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A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTELLIGENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT OF IXTH STANDARD STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study is an attempt to study the relationship between intelligence and achievement of IX standard students. A sample of 200 students is selected from nine higher secondary schools Out of 200 students 100 are boys and 100 are girls those who are studying in secondary and higher secondary schools in IX standard in age group of 14+. Data were collected and analyzed. It is found that there is a significant difference in respect of intelligence. The study aims to investigate the relationship between achievement and intelligence parents' level of education and occupations have no impact on the student's achievement and intelligence of the students.

Keywords:

Students, intelligence, achievement, education.

Cite This Article: P.Ruckmani, "A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTELLIGENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT OF IXTH STANDARD STUDENTS" International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah, Vol. 4, No. 5: SE (2016): 31-34.

1. INTRODUCTION

Good education that which draws out stimulates the spiritual intellectual and physical faculties of education. Education has a very important role in life. It is a threefold process. Imparting knowledge, developing knowledge and molding proper interests attitudes and values. B.Ed. education is an important and relevant education tool. To improve the future society a psychological approach towards the student is possible only through this education. So the achievement and intelligent goes hand in hand to improve the healthy future population. Hence, this study was taken by the investigator. Intelligence means intellect put to use. It is the use of intellectual abilities handling a situation or accomplishing any task. Achievement refers to one's learning attainments accomplishment proficiencies etc.,. Achievement is directly related to students growth and development in education situation. The term achievement is often understood in terms of students score test or examination. The student's performance is assessed by the marks one gets in the school subjects. The students are judged as high achievers and low achievers according to their level of achievement in their school subject.

2. HYPOTHESIS

To find out classification between an intelligence and achievement in the sub classes of boys and girls regarding gender, lower and higher income group regarding economic status literate and illiterate parents in terms of education and occupation.

3. METHODOLOGY

DESCRIPTIVE SURVEY DESIGN IS ADOPTED

The investigator took samples from the six urban and three rural schools. The investigator selected 100 girls and 100 boys as the samples with the age group of 14+ (9th standard) concentration was also given on the parents too for this study (ie) high income and low income as well as literate and illiterate parents.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESIS: 1

There is no significant difference between boys and girls is respect of achievement.

Table 1: The following table shows the interaction effect between boys and girls is achievement mean, SD and t value of achievement boys and girls.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value
Male	100	50.00	16.40	1.05
Female	100	52.50	17.30	

From the above table it is clear that the insignificant t value 1.05 which is less than table value 1.96 at 5% level therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls in respect of achievement. It is concluded that both boys and girls are in the same level achievement.

HYPOTHESIS: 2

There is no significant difference between the students whose parents belong to high income and low income in respect of achievement.

Table 2: Mean, S.D and t value of achievement high income and low income.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value
High income	115	52.70	8.60	2.65
Low income	28	53.40	10.36	

From the above table it is clear that the significant t value 2.65 which is greater than the table value 2.58 at 1% level. Therefore there is significant difference between high income and low income group in respect of achievement.

It is inferred that the students belong to high income parents and low income parents differed in their achievement.

HYPOTHESIS: 3

There is no significant difference between the students whose parents belong to higher level and lower level in respect of achievement.

Table 3: Mean, S.D and t value of achievement higher and lower occupation group.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value
Higher occupation	75	52.50	10.05	1.56
Higher occupation	125	50.00	12.602	

From the above table it is clear that the significant t value 1.56 which is less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level. Therefore there is no significant difference between the students parents are doing higher level occupation and lower level occupation in respect of achievement.

It is inferred that the student whose parents are doing higher and lower level jobs did not differ in their achievement.

HYPOTHESIS :4

There is no significant relationship between intelligence and academic achievement

Table 4:

Factors	Mean	r
Intelligence	51.25	0.99
Achievement	74.65	

Pearson's correlation co-efficient value **r** is found to be **0.99** which shows a high positive relationship between intelligence and academic achievement hence the hypothesis is rejected and it is inferred that there is significant relationship between intelligence and academic achievement.

5. FINDINGS

- The mean achievement score of IXth standard boys and girls are 50.00 and 52.50 respectively. The girls are superior to boys in achievement level.
- The students whose parents belong to high and low income group showed difference in their achievement
- The students whose parents belong to higher level occupation and lower level occupation did not differ in their achievement.
- There is significant relationship between students achievement score and intelligence scores (r =0.99)

6. CONCLUSION

The study aims to investigate the relationship between achievement and intelligence of the IXth standard students. Home environment and study habits play an important role in the development of academic achievement of students. Boys and girls are slightly differed in their academic achievement whereas no differences exist between them in respect of intelligence. Parents' levels of education and occupation have no impact on the students' achievement and intelligence of the students. Finally the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between achievement and intelligence of IXth standard students.

7. REFERENCES

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